

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Perceptions of Educational Stakeholders on the Introduction of Entrepreneurship Subject at Secondary Schools in Zanzibar

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Abstract

This study aimed at examining the perceptions of educational stakeholders on the introduction of entrepreneurship subjects at secondary schools in Zanzibar and the challenges of its integration. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Questionnaires, focus group discussions, and interviews were used in data collection. A sample of 67 respondents, 30 students, 30 teachers, 6 head teachers, and 1 educational officer was used. The study employed stratified sampling and purposive sampling techniques in selecting the sample. Purposive sampling was used to select the teachers, head teachers, and the educational officer while stratified sampling was used to sample the students. Interviews were conducted with head teachers and educational officers whereas focus group discussions and questionnaires were administered to students and teachers respectively. The data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20, while data collected using interviews and focus group discussion was analyzed qualitatively. The results were unequivocal as about 89.6% of respondents accepted the idea of the introduction of entrepreneurship subjects at secondary schools. Meanwhile, the findings showed that the integration would be faced with a myriad of challenges such as a shortage of competent entrepreneurship subject teachers, a shortage of teaching and learning materials, and the use of traditional teaching methods. The study recommended that the entrepreneurship subject can be introduced at secondary schools in Zanzibar but the use of modern teaching methods, frequent training of entrepreneurship subject teachers, and teaching entrepreneurship subject in an appropriate environment must be respected for better performance.

Keywords: Perception, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship subject, educational stakeholders

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1.Introduction

Unemployment has become a global challenge. Education has always been considered a foundation for solving problems of unemployment but this assertion is becoming invalid with the increasing number of jobless secondary school graduates. One of the ways of ensuring that education assists in addressing national and global unemployment are by incorporating entrepreneurship education into the school curriculum. Entrepreneurship education seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills, and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Some scholars have provided insights on the issue of the introduction of entrepreneurship education. According to Gautama, M., and Kumar, S.(2015) a growing

number of universities are pursuing research in entrepreneurship and establishing education programs, courses, activities, and services to promote entrepreneurial spirit and train entrepreneurs. Different countries have introduced entrepreneurship subjects in their education system. Mahadevan *et al* (2017) said that nowadays entrepreneurship education has been offered at all levels of schooling from primary or secondary schools to the university level. However, there is a difference in terms of the extent to which entrepreneurial education has been incorporated at different levels.

In Tanzania with particular reference to Zanzibar, entrepreneurship subject is being considered to be taught in higher-level education. The Zanzibar Education Policy (ZEP) of 2006 is silent about entrepreneurial